

SURGICAL TREATMENT IN ISOLATED LIVER TRAUMA**Dragos F. Voicu***MD, PhD.,**Braila County Emergency Hospital**Associated Profesor**“Dunarea de Jos” University, Galati – Romania***Adrian Drăgan***MD., Braila County Emergency Hospital***Abstract**

Isolated liver trauma represents an important cause of morbidity and mortality in the context of abdominal injuries. Due to its anatomical position and rich vascularization, the liver is one of the most frequently affected organs in both blunt and penetrating abdominal trauma. Management of these injuries has evolved significantly over recent decades with the introduction of modern imaging techniques and non-operative approaches. The aim of this study is to analyze the particularities of diagnosis, classification, and surgical treatment of isolated liver trauma, as well as the factors influencing patient outcomes.

Keywords: liver trauma, isolated hepatic injury, surgical treatment.

INTRODUCTION

Isolated liver trauma represents a major public health problem, particularly among young, active individuals frequently involved in road traffic accidents, falls from height, or assaults. Because of its anatomical position beneath the diaphragm and its rich dual vascular supply from the portal vein and hepatic artery, the liver is highly susceptible to severe injury in abdominal trauma.

Recent advances in imaging, particularly contrast-enhanced computed tomography (CT), and the development of conservative management protocols have significantly changed therapeutic strategies, reducing the need for exploratory laparotomy. Nevertheless, accurate assessment of injury severity and the patient's hemodynamic stability remain essential in determining optimal management.

This work aims to provide a synthetic presentation of the epidemiological, diagnostic, and therapeutic aspects of isolated liver trauma, as well as an overview of possible complications and patient prognosis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

We present the results of a retrospective, single-center study conducted between January 1, 2005 and December 31, 2024 (20 years). All patients with isolated liver trauma who underwent surgical treatment at

the First Department of General Surgery, Brăila County Emergency Clinical Hospital, were included.

Inclusion criteria:

Patients diagnosed with primary hepatic trauma (without significant injury to other abdominal or thoracic organs);

Surgical treatment performed at the study center within the mentioned period;

Complete clinical, imaging, and operative data available in medical charts.

Exclusion criteria:

Hepatic trauma associated with significant lesions of other organs (spleen, kidney, colon, lungs);

Postoperatively transferred patients lacking pre-operative data;

Missing or incomplete medical records. According to these criteria, 12 patients were included (12 cases over 20 years). Data were collected retrospectively from clinical registries and patient records. Collected variables included: age, sex, mechanism of trauma, AAST grade of hepatic lesion, type of surgical procedure, transfusion requirements, complications, and postoperative outcomes.

**Patient Characteristics and Clinical–Operative Data
(H – length of hospitalization/days)**

Nr.	Age	Gender	Traumatic mechanism	AAST degree	Operation type	Transfusions (U)	Complications	H	Evolution
1.	25	M	Road accident	II	Hepatorrhaphy	2	-	8	cured
2.	47	F	Precipitation	III	Hepatorrhaphy + packing	4	Minor bile leak	12	cured
3.	35	M	Direct blow trauma (sport)	I	Simple suture	0	-	7	cured
4.	52	M	Road accident	IV	Packing + Pringle	6	Rebleeding (repeat surgery)	18	cured
5.	60	F	Precipitation	III	Hepatorrhaphy + hemostats	3	-	10	cured
6.	28	M	Bull gore injury	V	Atypical hepatectomy	8	Sepsis post-operator	21	cured
7.	50	M	Penetrating trauma	V	Packing + suture	5	Rebleeding (repeat surgery) Liver abscess	19	deceased
8.	33	F	Precipitation	II	Hepatorrhaphy	2	-	9	cured
9.	44	M	Road accident	IV	Packing	6	Bile leak	16	cured
10.	52	M	Road accident	III	Hepatorrhaphy	4	-	11	cured
11.	38	F	Precipitation	II	Hepatorrhaphy	2	-	8	cured
12.	55	M	Road accident	IV	Segmentectomy	7	Recurrent hemorrhage	20	deceased

Surgical treatment was indicated mainly for patients with refractory hemodynamic instability or massive hemoperitoneum. The techniques used included hepatorrhaphy, perihepatic packing, Pringle maneuver, segmental liver resection, and the application of topical hemostatic agents. All patients underwent subhepatic drainage.

RESULTS

Out of 12 patients, 8 (66.7%) were male and 4 (33.3%) female, with a mean age of 42.2 ± 10.5 years (range 25–60 years). The most common mechanism of injury was road traffic accident (7 cases, 58.3%), followed by falls from height (4 cases, 33.3%) and penetrating trauma (2 cases, 8.4%).

Injury severity (AAST classification):

Grade I: 1 case (8.3%)

Grade II: 3 cases (25.0%)

Grade III: 4 cases (33.3%)

Grade IV: 3 cases (25.0%)

Grade V: 1 case (8.3%)

The most frequent surgical procedures were simple hepatorrhaphy (5 cases, 41.6%) and perihepatic packing (3 cases, 25%). The Pringle maneuver was used in 2 patients (16.6%). Segmental resections were

performed in 2 cases (16.6%). The average number of transfused blood units was 4.1 ± 2.2 U (range 0–8 U).

Postoperative complications occurred in 5 patients (41.6%): bile fistula in 2 cases (16.6%), hepatic abscess in 1 case (8.3%), recurrent bleeding in 2 cases (16.6%), and sepsis in 1 case (8.3%). Two patients (16.6%) required reoperation.

The average hospital stay was 13.8 ± 4.9 days (range 7–21 days).

There were two deaths (16.6%), both in patients with severe hepatic injuries (grade IV–V) complicated by recurrent bleeding and sepsis.

The results indicate that conservative surgical techniques (hepatorrhaphy, packing) can provide effective hemorrhage control in most cases of isolated liver trauma. High-grade lesions (IV–V) remain associated with significant morbidity and mortality.

DISCUSSION

Liver trauma continues to represent a major challenge in emergency surgery due to the organ's rich vascularization and the risk of massive bleeding. Over recent decades, there has been a global trend toward non-operative management in hemodynamically stable patients; however, surgical intervention remains indispensable for unstable patients or those with massive hemoperitoneum.

Although limited by the small number of cases, our study confirms that conservative surgical techniques—hepatorrhaphy and perihepatic packing—can effectively control bleeding in low- to moderate-grade injuries. In severe cases, the Pringle maneuver and segmental resections were used as necessary interventions, carrying a higher risk of complications and mortality.

The complication rate (41.6%) aligns with the data in the literature, where reported rates range from 30–50% in surgically managed hepatic trauma. Biliary fistulas, hepatic abscesses, and secondary hemorrhages represent the dominant complications, reflecting the complexity of achieving hemostasis and the fragility of posttraumatic hepatic parenchyma. The mean hospitalization time (≈ 14 days) is consistent with other small series, and mortality (16.6%) falls within reported ranges (10–20%) for high-grade injuries (IV–V).

Advances in perioperative resuscitation, bleeding control, and intensive postoperative care have contributed to improved survival outcomes.

The study's limitations include the small sample size, single-center design, and long data collection period, during which protocols and technologies have evolved. Nevertheless, the analysis contributes to understanding the surgical management of isolated hepatic trauma in a local clinical setting.

CONCLUSIONS

Isolated liver trauma remains a rare but potentially lethal condition.

Surgical treatment is reserved for cases with hemodynamic instability or massive hemoperitoneum.

Conservative surgical techniques (hepatorrhaphy, packing) are effective for most low- and moderate-grade injuries.

High-grade lesions (IV–V) are associated with higher morbidity and mortality, requiring multidisciplinary management and intensive support.

An individualized approach, based on hemodynamic status and injury extent, provides the best outcomes.

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